

WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE'S WORKS

Shirinova Mohira Baxtiyorjon qizi

Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti 2-bosqich magistratura talabasi[https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.7606856](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7606856)

Annotation: This article contains brief information about the works and tragedies of William Shakespeare. William Shakespeare's works are a treasure for world literature; this man was an English poet, dramatist and stage actor who lived between the XVI and XVII centuries. Shakespeare's plays include comedies, historical dramas and tragedies.

Key words: William Shakespeare, Romeo and Juliet, Sonnets, Othello, Hamlet, King Lear.

William Shakespeare is an English playwright, poet and actor, one of the most famous playwrights in the world, the author of a cycle of at least 17 comedies, 10 chronicles, 11 tragedies, 5 poems and 154 sonnets.

The works of William Shakespeare: Antony and Cleopatra(1606), Hamlet(1601), Julius Caesar(1598), King John(1605), Antony and Cleopatra(1606), Richard II, Romeo and Juliet, Sonnets, The Tempest, Timon of Athens, Titus Andronicus, Troilus and Cressida, Timon of Athens, The Two Gentlemen of Verona, The Two Noble Kinsmen, The Winter's Tale, Venus and Adonis, Othello, Pericles, Richard III, The Merry Wives of Windsor, Much Ado About Nothing.

Sonnets- A special place in the creative heritage of William Shakespeare is occupied by "Sonnets", in which the poet brilliantly conveyed the complex range of human experiences, the beauty and strength of feelings imbued with genuine passion. Admiration for the perfection of a friend is closely intertwined here with the theme of reckless love for the mysterious "dark lady". Through the image of a lyrical hero, the story of a beautiful, great and immortal human soul is shown. "With this key, Shakespeare opened his heart" (W. Wordsworth). The masterpiece of world poetry is presented in the translation by S. Ya. Marshak, which is rightfully considered a classic, and decorated with magnificent illustrations by Charles Robinson.

"Othello" is one of the pinnacles of William Shakespeare's work. This is a story not only about great love and the tragedy of deceived trust, but also about the conflict between a hero who wants to live according to the laws of truth and justice, and a society that is indifferent and hostile to human values. The immortal tragedy is perfectly complemented by illustrations by the British painter J. Gilbert.

Hamlet. The events leading up to the start of Hamlet set the stage for the tragedy. When Hamlet's father, the King of Denmark, dies suddenly, Hamlet's mother Gertrude marries his uncle Claudius, who becomes the new king. A ghost claiming to be the ghost of Hamlet's father describes his murder at the hands of Claudius and demands that Hamlet avenge the murder. When the counselor Polonius learns from his daughter Ophelia that Hamlet came to him in a distracted state, Polonius attributes the prince's condition to lovesickness and sets a trap for Hamlet, using Ophelia as bait. To accept Claudius's guilt, Hamlet prepares a play that simulates the murder; Claudius' attitude is that of a guilty man. Hamlet, now free to act, mistakenly kills Polonius for Claudius. Claudius sends Hamlet away as part of a deadly plot. After the death of Polonius, Ophelia goes mad and then drowns. Returning safely to confront the king, Hamlet

agrees to a match of swordsmanship with Laertes, Ophelia's brother, who secretly poisons his own rapier. At the meeting, Claudius prepares poisoned wine for Hamlet, which Gertrude unknowingly drinks; when he dies, he blames Claudius, whom Hamlet kills. Then first Laertes and then Hamlet die, both victims of Laertes' rapier.

King Lear dramatizes the story of an elderly king of ancient Britain whose plan to divide his kingdom between his three daughters ends in tragedy. Her older daughters Goneril and Regan flatter her as she tests each one by asking how much they love her. Cordelia, the youngest, does not, and Lear rejects and banishes her. She marries the King of France. Goneril and Regan steal from Lear and make him wander madly in a raging storm. Meanwhile, Edmund, the Earl of Gloucester's illegitimate son, pits Gloucester against his own legitimate son, Edgar. Gloucester, horrified by his daughters' treatment of Lear, receives word that the French army is coming to help Lear. Edmund betrays Gloucester to Regan and her husband Cornwall, who opens Gloucester's eyes and makes Edmund Earl of Gloucester.

Romeo and Juliet. In the prologue of Romeo and Juliet, the main characters are called "star-crossed lovers" and the stars seem to conspire against these young lovers. Romeo - Montague, Juliet - Capulet. Their families are embroiled in conflict, but the moment they meet - when Romeo and his friends attend a party at Juliet's house in disguise - the two fall in love and quickly decide to marry. A monk secretly marries them in hopes of ending the feud. Romeo and his companions almost immediately encounter Juliet's cousin Tybalt, who turns against Romeo. When Romeo refuses to fight, Romeo's friend Mercutio accepts the challenge and is killed. Romeo then kills Tybalt and is banished. He spends that night with Juliet and then leaves for Mantua. Juliet's father forces her to marry Count Paris. To avoid such a marriage, Juliet takes a potion given by a monk that makes her appear dead. When Romeo wakes up, the monk sends a message to his family to be at his grave. The plan goes awry and Romeo learns that she is dead. Romeo kills himself in the tomb. Juliet wakes up, sees his dead body, and commits suicide. Their deaths finally appear to end the feud.

In conclusion, Shakespeare's works have a great influence on the development of world literature. Especially, his translations have gained incomparable importance in all Eastern and Western countries. Romeo and Juliet, "Hamlet", "King Lear" are in the hearts of book readers. Of course, reading Shakespeare's works is difficult, but very interesting. Shakespeare had a great influence on the development of theater art. His tragedies are among the masterpieces of world literature. Shakespeare's works are still alive today. Despite all his hard work and fame, William Shakespeare did not receive any awards or diplomas.

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